

AN IMPROVED ECC ALGORITHM FOR SECURE CLOUD STORAGE SYSTEM WITH THE HELP OF SHA-256 BASED USER AUTHENTICATION AND DEEP LEARNING BASED INTRUSION DETECTION SYSTEM

I. AROCKIA ANTONY SAMY*

Research Scholar, Department of Computer Science, St. Xavier's College, Affiliated to Manonmaniam Sundaranar University, Abishekapatti, Tirunelveli, Tamil Nadu, India. E-mail: antonyammu75@gmail.com

DR. M. SAFISH MARY

Assistant Professor, Department of Computer Science, St Xavier's College, Affiliated to Manonmaniam Sundaranar University, Abishekapatti, Tirunelveli, Tamil Nadu, India. E-mail: marysafish@gmail.com

Abstract:

A cloud environment is a collection of resources used to provide on-demand services to cloud clients. Access to the cloud environment is supplied through internet services, and data kept in the cloud environment is more accessible to both internal and external invaders. At the moment, cloud security experts are unable to provide a more dependable, safe, and effective intrusion detection system (IDS) for identifying intruders in data transfer. For fulfilling this requirement, in this paper a novel deep learning (DL) model namely Wavelet Kernel including Multi-Layer Perceptron Neural Network (WKMLPNN) based IDS is proposed for identifying the attacks while performing cloud data transmission. Additionally, to offer cloud secure storage, Improved Elliptical Curve Cryptography (IECC) is proposed with a novel key generation mechanism. Initially, the cloud user or data owner (DO) is registered with the Cloud Service Provider (CSP) for uploading their data to the cloud. Then at the CSP end, the authenticity of the DO is checked by implementing the Secure Hash Algorithm 256 (SHA-256) technique. After successful authentication, the DO is allowed to upload their data to the cloud. The CSP receives the data from the DO and then the intrusion present in the received data is identified using novel IDS (WKMLPNN). The presented IDS follows three operations such as preprocessing, optimal feature selection using Time factor incorporated Gravitational Search Algorithm (TGSA) and WKMLPNN applied classification for identifying the intrusions present in the data. If the received data contain the intrusion, the data will be avoided and not stored in the cloud, otherwise, the data will be stored in the cloud securely using the IECC algorithm. Finally, if the cloud users request CSP for data retrieval, the authenticity of the user is again checked using the SHA-256 algorithm. If the user is an authenticated one, the retrieval permission is granted for him, otherwise, the permission is denied for the user. The simulation results reveal that the presented approach outperforms existing strategies for intrusion categorization and encryption.

Key words: Cloud Computing, Cloud Security, Intrusion Detection System, Encryption Algorithms, Deep Learning, User Authentication.

1. INTRODUCTION

The expansion of digital data transfer frequently presents new challenges, such as large investments in the procurement and storage of extra hardware, software, as well as networking resources. Businesses are increasingly turning to cloud storage services to address this problem [1]. Cloud computing is a network access framework which provides ubiquitous,

suitable, as well as on-demand network access for a pool of shared configurable computing resources such as servers, networks, storage, along with applications, which can be provisioned rapidly and released with a lesser effort of management or interaction from service providers [2, 3, 4, and 5]. The primary purpose of cloud storage is to store user data on an off-site storage system of the cloud maintained by a third-party CSP. In current times, most owners prefer to save their data on the cloud because of the services provided by cloud vendors rather than on their system hard drive or other memory devices. After the owner's data is stored on a remote database, it will be available via an internet link betwixt the user and cloud databases [6]. Attacks on cloud environments are on the rise, coinciding with significant advances in information and communication technologies. Individuals and organizations are increasingly concerned with preventing system threats and guaranteeing data security [7]. The IDS has evolved into a significant tool for monitoring malicious activity as well as triggering alerts for identifying suspicious attacks. The motivation for using IDS is because of the following security principles: integrity, confidentiality along with the availability of data is compromised owing to intrusions and (or) attacks such as traffic analysis, spoofing, cyber-attacks and other types of harmful vulnerabilities [8]. The intrusion detection systems (IDSs) are divided into two types. Signature-based IDSs look for well-known attack patterns on the network. Anomaly-based IDSs are more advanced systems that can detect unknown attacks even if they have never been seen before [9]. The main issue with such systems is the incapability of detecting unforeseen attacks and the frequent manual updating of the signature database. This makes it difficult to detect zero-day attacks. The anomaly-based system, on the other hand, detects malicious action based on deviation from a group of baseline functionalities. The zero-day attacks are detected by these IDSs. However, the major disadvantage of anomaly-based systems is their inability to detect legitimate traffic with better accuracy. As a result, the FPR will be increased. Hybrid systems, alternatively, unite the above two approaches for achieving a higher detection rate with a low FPR [10].

Recently, machine learning (ML) approaches were utilized for training the IDS to detect malicious network traffic. The key idea behind ML-based IDS is to find patterns in the dataset as well as build IDS around them. The IDS is capable of detecting adequately [11]. Over the last few years, most researchers have used ML methods such as Support Vector Machine [12], Logistic Regression [13], K-nearest Neighbors (KNN) [14], and others to perform efficient IDS for cloud platforms and have reported good results. Their limitations in terms of data complexity, however, give rise to DL methods. Because of its dominance in training large data sets, DL is gaining significant traction in every field of study [15]. This paper proposes a novel DL framework for detecting intrusions during end-to-end data transmission in the cloud. The detection framework determines whether or not the intrusion is present in the user's uploaded file. To identify malicious data behaviour, it is necessary to provide security to data that is classified as normal after intrusion detection (ID). To maintain privacy, data must be encrypted before storage, i.e., the data must be encrypted locally before being stored in the cloud, and cloud providers cannot retrieve any information from the encrypted data without the users' permission. These stringent security requirements make its effective use difficult, particularly for indexing and searching outsourced encrypted data on

the public cloud [16]. Wired and wireless network cryptography is used in cloud computing to protect different kinds of data like email data, credit card data, together with corporate data. The two types of cryptography are symmetric and asymmetric cryptography. Access control, confidentiality, authentication, availability, integrity as well as non-repudiation are all important goals of cryptography [17].

Many authentication methods, such as integrated key cryptography (IKC), encryption algorithms, such as Advanced Encryption Standard (AES), Rivest Shamir Adleman (RSA), Blowfish, Data Encryption Standard (DES), and their modified and improved versions, are currently being developed to ensure secure data transmission in the cloud. Nonetheless, those methods are vulnerable to a variety of malware attacks as well as security threats [18]. Thus, using an improved version of the ECC algorithm and a SHA-256-based user authentication framework, this paper introduced a technique for normal data security after ID in cloud servers. Keeping the shortcomings of existing cloud platform ID and encryption methods in mind, this paper proposes novel mechanisms with the following goals:

- To propose an efficient SHA-256 hashing based user authentication system for preventing the data from unauthorized access both in data upload and in data download phases.
- To present a novel DL based ID framework namely WKMLPNN for finding out the intrusions presents in the cloud platform when performing end to end data transmission.
- To propose an efficient and optimal feature selection mechanism for IDS with the help of TGSA with an aim to reduce the training time and to improve the classification performance.
- To propose an IECC algorithm based cloud storage system for providing high level of security to the non intrusion data after performing intrusion detection.
- To analyze the performance of the current research model by comparing them with the existing models regarding some performance metrics.

The rest of the paper is listed as follows: in section 2, a literature survey of some of the prior systems related to the proposed model is provided; in section 3, a brief explanation of the proposed research framework is presented; in section 4, the effectiveness of the proposed research model is evaluated as a result and discussion part; and finally, section 5 includes the paper's conclusion as well as future work.

2. RELATED WORKS

This section surveys recent state-of-the-art techniques regarding intrusion detection frameworks, and cloud security. The techniques that combine both detection and securities are also discussed. The models are surveyed based on their research objective; a technique developed and achieved results. Finally, the problem statement is drawn for the surveyed techniques and the aim of using the proposed research methodology is given.

2.1 Intrusion Detection Frameworks

Doddi Srilatha and Gopal K. Shyam [19] developed the cloud-based IDS that combined kernel fuzzy c-means clustering (KFCM) and an ideal type-2 fuzzy neural network (OT2FNN). T2FNN parameters were optimally selected for weight optimization employing the lion optimization technique (LOA). The suggested IDS identified the intrusion and permitted only normal data to be saved in the cloud. This system, however, leads to a longer execution time when grouping non-linear data based on the prior selection of different clusters. **Parul Singh and Virender Ranga [20]** developed an effectual network-based ID model which used an ensemble-based ML approach. The ensemble approach here used four classifiers i.e., subspace discriminant, bagged tree, boosted tree, and RUSBooted along with a voting system for performing ID. For testing the suggested mode, the CICIDS 2017 dataset and the CloudSim simulator were used. The outcomes showed that the model attained a higher detection rate as well as a lesser false alarm rate than some state-of-the-art techniques. However, there are noteworthy downsides when using ensemble methods such as lack of explainability, which leads to degradation of performance in classification. **Linbin Wen [21]** presented a Back Propagation Neural Network (BPNN) for cloud ID. An improved artificial bee colony algorithm (IABC) was utilized to perform optimization in BPNN. The combination of IABC with BPNN attained the average ID rate of 92.67%. However, the model is sluggish and untrustworthy because the BPNN's actual performance on a specific problem is dependent on the input data. **Krishna Tummalapalli S.R and A. S. N. Chakravarthy [22]** introduced cloud IDS with clustering and two-level classification models. Firstly, a Bayesian fuzzy clustering was used to cluster the nodes in the cloud. Then for identifying the intrusions present in clusters, a two-level gravitational group search-based support vector neural network (GG-SVNN) was used. The GG-SVNN classifier gave an accuracy of 92.41% and a false alarm rate of 4.75%. Support vectors, on the other hand, are not suitable for large data sets. Furthermore, the classifier will not perform accurately if the counts of features for each data point go beyond the number of training data samples. **Rajendra Patil et al. [23]** suggested a hypervisor level distributed network security (HLDNS) approach that was implemented on each cloud computing processing server. The feasible features were extracted from cloud network traffic using a binary bat algorithm (BBA) with two fitness functions. To detect the intrusions, the extracted features were fed into the random forest classifier and after ID, the intrusion alerts were generated. For detecting the distributed attack and for generating a new attack signature, the intrusion alerts from different servers were associated. However, the HLDNS framework doesn't include any intrusion prevention framework by integrating it with a suitable encryption mechanism.

2.2 Encryption Techniques

Muhammad Tahir et al. [24] suggested a model based on a genetic algorithm (GA) for generating the keys for performing encryption and decryption of cryptographic algorithm. This combination of the optimal key-based cryptographic model was utilized by the author for ensuring the privacy and integrity of cloud data. The CryptoGA included with the cryptographic model provided better outcomes on selected parameters when contrasted with

RSA, DES, AES, 3DES, and Blowfish. However, the implementation of GA for optimal key generation is a time-consuming process and the model is highly complex. **Venkata Koti Reddy Gangireddy et al.** [25] introduced a cyber security framework with the process of optimal key generation for enhancing cloud data security. Here, to cluster the secret data, k-medoid clustering was utilized. The clustered data was then encrypted and stored in the cloud with the help of the blowfish encryption model. To enhance the blowfish model's accuracy, an improved dragonfly algorithm was used. However, the conventional blowfish approach has a 64-bit block size. Owing to the small block size, the model is more at risk for attacks. **Chinnasamy P et al.** [26] combined ECC as well as blowfish for providing security to the healthcare data which was stored in the cloud. The hybrid system's performance was compared to the previous methods, and the results revealed that the method provided greater security and confidentiality to the patient data. However, the methods are presented without any modifications in both ECC and blowfish, which increases the attacker's ability to retrieve the key of the data quickly and allows the attacker to easily access the medical data. **Fursan Thabit et al.** [27] suggested a lightweight cryptographic (LWC) mechanism to enhance the cloud data security. The model was inspired by feistel as well as substitution permutation architectural techniques, which improved the encryption's complexity. Shannon's theory of diffusion as well as confusion was achieved via the use of logical operations like (XOR, XNOR, shifting along with swapping). When compared to the cryptographic systems commonly used in cloud computing, the algorithm's results showed a high level of security. However, because the entire block must be captured for encryption and decryption, the model has the disadvantage of slower encryption speed. The modes also breed errors because a single symbol error can change the entire block. For performing user data encryption in the cloud, **Rabia Abid et al.** [28] suggested an optimized Homomorphic Encryption Chinese Remainder Theorem with a RSA (HE-CRT-RSA) algorithm. For efficient communication and security, the technique used multiple keys. The algorithm's result showed improved performance with shorter decryption times. The model HE-CRT-RSA was found to be 3–4% faster than the traditional RSA. The generation of multiple keys for encryption and decryption, on the other hand, increases the algorithm's processing time, lowering the system's performance.

2.3 Intrusion Detection with Encryption

Avijit Mondal [29] presented an ID approach for detecting malicious attacks when performing data communication or data storage in the cloud. For identifying the malicious behavior, the Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) was used. The CNN categorizes the data as attacked and non attacked data. After detection, the non-attacked data was stored in the cloud using a honeypot algorithm. Efficiently the method founded a web service attack and sufficiently increased the regularity of the web service attack detection as well as decreased the alarming rate. Honeypot security, on the other hand, has its limits, as it cannot detect security vulnerabilities in legitimate systems and does not always identify the perpetrator. An attacker could even travel laterally to infiltrate the real production network after successfully exploiting the honeypot. **Osama Alkadi et al.** [30] presented a Deep Blockchain Framework (DBF) for offering security-centered distributed IDS in the cloud. Additionally, a blockchain

(BC) with smart contracts was used for providing privacy to the ID engines. For dealing with sequential network data, the ID method was utilized by a Bidirectional Long Short-Term Memory (BiLSTM). The BC framework along with smart contracts was developed with the help of the Ethereum library for offering privacy towards the distributed ID engines. The outcomes revealed that DBF performed better than other challenging models. However, the weakness of using BC in privacy-preserving is its scalability, while BC was not indestructible. And also, the BC can lead to complexity, and it can also be inefficient. **Beibei Li et al.** [31] presented a federated DL scheme, named DeepFed, for identifying cyber threats performed in industrial CPSs. In addition, for preserving the model parameters' security as well as privacy with the help of the training process, a secure communication protocol namely the Paillier cryptosystem was established. Experiments demonstrated the higher efficiency of the DeepFed system in detecting different sorts of cyberattacks in industrial CPSs as well as the effectual performance over high-tech schemes. To train the model, however, federated learning necessitates substantially more local device power and memory. By utilizing the benefits afforded by the BC, **Wenjuan Li et al.** [32] introduced a BC challenge-based collaborative intrusion detection networks (CIDN) framework. By evaluating the received feedback and alert rankings, the framework enabled nodes for generating a consortium chain and improved the robustness of challenge-based CIDNs. The results showed that the framework improved the resilience of CIDNs in the areas of trust management utilizing detecting advanced malicious nodes and alarm aggregation by recognizing untruthful inputs as well as diminishing error rates in both random poisoning and SOOA tests.

2.4 Problem Statement

The drawbacks of the above-surveyed techniques are already discussed. This section highlights the problems faced by the existing models in cloud security and in ID frameworks. The models used in ID frameworks [19-23], mostly used optimization mechanisms in the weight selection of the classifier and they did not focus on developing efficient feature selection mechanisms for classifiers. This will increase the training time of the classifier for classifying the intrusions, so the performance of the classifier is degraded with overfitting issues and lesser accuracy. In addition, the works are mainly developed to find out the intrusions performed in the data transmission process, whereas no additional focus is given to intrusion prevention systems. This will increase the chances of intruders attacking the normal data while stored in the cloud after ID. The existing encryption methodologies [24-28] either use hybrid mechanisms or optimal key generation processes for providing data security to the cloud. The use of optimization mechanisms in the key generation process of encryption models increases the algorithm's processing time, as well as the complexity of the models and the existing optimization models for key generation have the problems of premature convergence and local optima, which will further reduce the algorithm's performance. Most of the developed existing hybrid encryption schemes are comes without any modification in their basic processes. In addition, they only provided encryption to the user data, where the authentication of the cloud user cannot be performed in the models. As a result, anyone can get access to the user data which is stored in the cloud and there is a high possibility of decrypting the data easily by performing basic operations of encryption models. So it is

necessary to develop a highly secure encryption model with an efficient authentication scheme. The models such as [29-32] are developed to achieve both ID and prevention for cloud data. However, they failed to achieve cloud user authentication when performing data transmission and data retrieval in the cloud. The classification models developed are not achieving the best performance because of increased time complexity, and also poor algorithm design. In previously generated encryption algorithms, the data integrity rate was not accessed. They failed to address the better security issue, as well as to achieve a higher data integrity rate and a shorter processing time. In addition, only less number of works are developed to focus on both ID and security. So from the survey of the existing mechanism, it is clear that authentication, ID after data transmission, and providing security to the non-attacked data in the cloud with an efficient mechanism are required for cloud computing platforms. So this paper overcomes the issues of previously developed models by proposing three efficient schemes such as user authentication, ID, and data encryption. Initially, the SHA256 hashing based authentication framework is provided for ensuring the authenticity of the user for uploading the data to the cloud. The CSP receives this data and to identify the sensitivity level of the received data at the CSP end, a novel WKMLPNN is proposed with an optimal feature selection mechanism. The classified sensitive data is stored in the cloud by encrypting the data using the IECC algorithm. Finally, the authentication is performed again at the user end using the SHA-256 hashing technique if the user requests data access for the data which is stored in the cloud. Using these novel mechanisms for cloud platforms increases the cloud data security level by achieving efficient authentication and ID frameworks with lesser complexity, lesser processing time, and remarkable performance.

3. PROPOSED METHODOLOGY

In this paper, a unique encryption technique, IECC, is developed for providing security to cloud user data by including user authentication and an ID framework. In the first phase of the proposed system, the DO who wishes to store data in the cloud registers with the CSP. Following successful registration, the cloud user is authenticated using CSP by matching the hash code and One Time Password (OTP) before the user data is uploaded into the cloud. The sensitivity level of the data (intrusion present in the data) from the cloud user is then recognized using a novel DL model called WKMLPNN, which categorizes the data as sensitive or non-sensitive. Preprocessing, feature selection, and classification are used to classify intrusions in input data. The data uploaded from the DO has recognized whether or not it contains any incursions based on the training. The sensitive data that must be safeguarded in the cloud is non-intrusion data. At the CSP end, sensitive data is secured with an IECC algorithm, and the best key for this operation is created with a CMBA algorithm. If there is data intrusion in the data, it indicates that the data is avoided, and only data without intrusion can be preserved in the cloud in an encrypted manner. If they DO requests data retrieval from the CSP, the DO is authenticated at the CSP end, and access is granted to the owner for data retrieval if the owner is authenticated. Figure 1 depicts the suggested model's architecture.

Figure 1: Proposed architecture

3.1 User Registration

Initially, the DO who wants to use cloud storage services must register with the CSP. The DO wishes to submit his personal information, including a valid username, user ID, password, and mobile number, in order to register with the CSP. The information submitted by the user is saved at the CSP end. However, the SALT (a random value in any range) concatenates the password, increasing the security of the password by combining a random string with the password given by registered users. The password obtained using SALT, user ID, and timestamp are then concatenated and hashed with the SHA-256 hashing algorithm. One of the most extensively used hash algorithms is the secure hash algorithm with digest size of 256 bits, also known as the SHA 256 algorithm. While other variations exist, SHA 256 has been at the forefront of real-world applications. SHA-256 is not substantially higher difficult to code than SHA-1 as well as has not yet been compromised. A hash is not an encryption function because once hashed it cannot be decrypted back to the real form (it is a kind of 'one-way' cryptographic function for any size of source text with a fixed size). This makes it suited for comparing 'hashed' copies of texts rather than decrypting the text to retrieve the original version. As a result, in this case, SHA-256 is utilized as a key for the Dos during the file uploading and downloading stages. For authentication purposes, the output hash code (256 bits) will be stored in both the user and CSP databases. The combination of the SALT and a user password prevents dictionary attacks, SQL injection attacks, as well as hash code generation, which prevents the CSP or an unauthorized entity from stealing user credentials from cloud storage. The user's registration is finished by submitting their information and generating a hash code.

3.2 Access Permission for Data Upload

If the user wants to upload data to the cloud after registering, the user should log in to the CSP first. The CSP validates the user by entering the user's information. At the time of login, the user is prompted to provide the hash code value obtained during registration. If the hash codes created during login and registration are matched, the CSP creates an OTP and sends it to the user's registered mobile number, which was provided at the time of registration process. The user is required to enter the sent OTP to the CSP in order to complete the certification process; the CSP compares it to the generated OTP and therefore verifies the mobile number if it matches; otherwise, the access permission is denied.

3.3 Intrusion Detection

The DO is permitted to keep data in cloud storage as soon as the user is registered with CSP. The DO does this by uploading the data to the cloud. To ensure the security level of the data received from the user at the CSP end, ID is performed using the DL model. The training part of ID is conducted using a publically available database, NSL-KDD, which is utilized to identify the intrusions contained in the DO's received data. The suggested ID system is trained in three stages: preprocessing, feature selection, and classification. Each of the phases is discussed below.

3.3.1 Preprocessing

The preprocessing of the proposed research methodology is performed in three ways: i) removal of missing values and redundant data, ii) numerical conversion, and iii) normalization. Each of the pre-processing operation is explained as follows:

i) Removal of missing values and redundant data

The dataset's data values are unprocessed and may include missing values along with redundant data packets. As a result, the dataset is preprocessed to remove duplicate and redundant instances as well as missing values.

ii) Numerical conversion

Some of the features in the dataset have multiple data formats. To fulfill with the classifiers on the given dataset, the features should be numerical or Boolean, rather than strings or characters. As a result, the features of the dataset can be transformed into numerical values using a single hot encoder, and the numerical converted dataset is normalized.

iii) Normalization

Normalization of datasets is a significant preprocessing technique, particularly in classification. Normalization is used to convert the dataset's attributes into values that are compatible with one another. Normalization speeds up operations on the dataset and increases the likelihood of successful results. The dataset is normalized by utilizing min-max normalization in this case. The largest and lowest values in a group are used in this procedure. All subsequent data is normalized to these values. The goal here is to normalize the smallest

value to 0 and the greatest value to 1, and to distribute all other data to this 0-1 range. The mathematical equation for the dataset's min-max normalization is as follows.

$$F_{nr} = \frac{F - Mn(F)}{Mx(F) - Mn(F)} \quad (1)$$

Where F denotes the original feature value, $Mn(F)$ denotes the minimum value of F , $Mx(F)$ specifies the maximum value of F and F_{nr} denotes the normalized value of F .

3.3.2 Feature Selection

By choosing the most significant variables and deleting redundant and irrelevant data, feature selection increases the prediction capacity of machine learning/ deep learning algorithms. Following preprocessing, TGSA is used to choose the optimum features of the preprocessed dataset. The Gravitational Search Algorithm (GSA) is a novel optimization model that is centered on gravity's law. GSA considers agents to be objects with masses. The heavier particles obtain more efficient solutions than lighter particles. All particles are attracted to one another by the law of gravity and move in accordance with the law of motion. When iteration increases, the populace will be drawn to the largest particle whose position within solution space indicates the ideal solution. However, when handling complex optimization problems, the typical GSA suffers from premature convergence. A time component (T) is included in traditional GSA in this study to improve its convergence speed and local search capacity. This modification in GSA is named TGSA. The steps are detailed as follows

Step 1: Generate the initial population of N individuals randomly in the search space by the following equation (2)

$$F_i^t = \{f_i^1, f_i^2, \dots, f_i^d, \dots, f_i^D(t)\}, i \in 1, 2, 3, \dots, N \quad (2)$$

$$f_i^d(t=0) \sim U(f_{\min}^d, f_{\max}^d) \quad (3)$$

Where f_i^d denotes the position of the i^{th} individual in d^{th} dimension and D denotes the total number of dimensions. The search space' boundary for d is represented by (f_{\min}^d, f_{\max}^d) . The velocities are initialized to the value of zero

$$K_i(t=0) = 0 \quad (4)$$

Step 2: The fitness function (Ob) for optimal feature selection using proposed GSA is computed by the following equation (5). In this research, the major goal of MLPNN is to develop efficient IDS based on TGSA, which plays an important role in feature selection to detect intrusions. The classifier's accuracy is used as an objective function. As a result, the fitness value of each agent is determined by the classifier's proper classification accuracy on the data. Throughout the evolutionary process, the fitness function seeks to maximize the classification accuracy obtained from the selected features.

$$Ob = Accuracy = \frac{A+B}{A+B+C+D} \quad (5)$$

Where $A, B, C,$ and D represents True Positive, True Negative, False Positive, as well as False Negative.

Step 3: After fitness evaluation, the best as well as worst fitness agent within the populace are identified at time t . In the problems of minimization, the best $A(t)$ along with worst $B(t)$ particles are defined using (6) and (7):

$$A(t) = \min_{i \in \{1, \dots, N\}} Ob_i(t) \quad (6)$$

$$B(t) = \max_{i \in \{1, \dots, N\}} Ob_i(t) \quad (7)$$

Where, N represents the size of the population, and $Ob_i(t)$ symbolizes the fitness value of particle i , which is evaluated by the fitness function.

Step 4: After the identification of $A(t)$ and $B(t)$, the updating phase of the populace is carried out. Firstly, the masses of the particles are updated. The mass of particle i , M_i^t , is mapped according to its fitness, $Ob_i(t)$

$$M_i^t = \frac{m_i^t}{\sum_{j=1}^n m_j^t} \quad (8)$$

$$m_i^t = \frac{Ob_i(t) - B(t)}{A(t) - B(t)} \quad (9)$$

Step 5: Next, the gravitational force $\{GF_{ij}^d(t)\}$ acting on agent i from agent j in d^{th} dimension is computed utilizing j^{th} agent mass M_j^t , and the i^{th} agent mass M_i^t . This process is mathematically evaluated as

$$GF_{ij}^d(t) = g_t \frac{M_i^t \cdot M_j^t}{Ed_{ij}^d + \epsilon} (Ob_j^d(t-1) - Ob_i^d(t-1)) \quad (10)$$

Where Ed_{ij}^d represents the Euclidean distance betwixt the particles i as well as j . The term ϵ is a small value of constant, which is included to the divisor for avoiding a division by zero once the particles are overlapping each other and the gravitational constant at time t is denoted as g_t , which can be computed as

$$g_t = g_0 \times e^{-\frac{\phi t}{R_t}} \quad (11)$$

Where, g_0 denotes the initial gravitational constant at the beginning of the search process, ϕ is another constant, and R_i is the total number of iterations.

Step 6: The total force acting on i^{th} agent in d^{th} dimension is

$$TF_i^d(t) = \sum_{j=1, j \neq i}^n R_j^d \cdot GF_{ij}^d(t) \quad (12)$$

Where, R denotes the uniformly distributed arbitrary number within the range between [0, 1] that offers an algorithm's stochastic feature.

Step 7: The GSA's particles move toward Newton's law of motion. In accordance with Newton's law, the i^{th} agent acceleration over d^{th} dimension, $\alpha_i^d(t)$ can be computed utilizing the below equation (13)

$$\alpha_i^d(t) = \frac{Ob_i^d(t)}{M_i^t} \quad (13)$$

Step 7: The next velocity of the agent i in d^{th} dimension is equivalent to a fraction of its current velocity in addition to its acceleration, which is denoted as

$$K_i(t+1) = R_i^d \times K_i(t) + \alpha_i^d(t) \quad (14)$$

Where R_i^d is a uniformly distributed arbitrary number in the range of [0, 1] that enhances the stochastic feature of the model's search. The i^{th} particle's next position in d^{th} dimension is expressed using eqn. (15):

$$F_i^d(t+1) = F_i^t + K_i(t+1) \quad (15)$$

In the standard GSA, the new positions are updated using the sum of the previous iteration and the current velocity. As shown in Eq. (15), there is a constant time factor (the default is "1") in the original position equation, which indicates that agents with velocity K_i fly to a new position for the regular time duration of "1". This flight state may lead to agents being trapped in the local optima. In fact, as the distance between agents and the global best solution decreases, the flight time of agents decreases. So here a time factor is incorporated in GSA as a non-linear function. The flight time is close to "1" during early iterations to increase GSA's convergence speed, and the flight time is close to "0" during later iterations to strengthen GSA's local search capability. After executing extensive tests, the time factor is defined, as shown in Eq. (16). Then, based on the time factor, the new position equation is expressed by Eq. (17).

$$\beta_t = 1 - e^{-\left(\frac{iter_{max} - iter}{iter_{max} + 0.6 * iter}\right)^{10}} \quad (16)$$

$$F_i^d(t+1) = F_i^t + \beta_t * K_i(t+1) \quad (17)$$

The above processes are continued until the stopping criterion is met, i.e. maximum number of iteration is reached.

3.3.3 Classification using WKDMLP

Following the selection of optimal features using TGSA, the selected features are fed into WKMLPNN for intrusion classification. The Multi-Layer Perceptron Neural Network (MLPNN) model, shown in Fig. 2, was the first and most widely used among DL methods. MLPNN based prediction models are commonly used to solve complex nonlinear problems in classification and regression. The MLPNN is essentially a feed-forward model with one input layer, one or more hidden layers, and one output layer. The first layer's neurons receive input from the outside world, whereas subsequent layers' neurons receive input from the output of neurons from previous layers. Weights are assigned to the connections between the layers in order to control the effect of related input on neurons. Each neuron in MLPNN produces output by sequentially using summation and activation functions. However, because the weights between the input layer and the hidden layer, as well as the hidden layer biases of the MLPNN, are chosen at random during training, good training accuracy cannot be guaranteed every time. To address these issues, a wavelet kernel (WK) function is incorporated into conventional MLPNN, which replaces the original MLPNN method of randomly selecting the input weights and hidden layer biases. The WKMLPNN method outperforms basic MLPNN in terms of non-linear function approximation and data classification.

Figure 2: Structure of MLPNN

The initial layer of the network is an input layer, which takes in an input, which will be used to produce an output. The inputs of the WKMLPNN are the optimally selected features from TGSA. The initialization of input features can be denoted by equation (18)

$$S_i = S_1, S_2, \dots, S_n \quad (18)$$

These inputs are fed into the hidden layer. In the presented model, two hidden layers are used. The output of the first (H_j) and second hidden layer (H_k) is expressed using the equations (19) and (20)

$$H_j = \sum_{i,j}^n W_{ij} S_i + b_j \quad (19)$$

$$H_k = \sum_{j,k}^n W_{jk} H_j + b_k \quad (20)$$

Where W_{ij} denotes the weight value of the i^{th} input layer to the j^{th} hidden layer, W_{jk} denotes the weight value of the j^{th} hidden layer to the k^{th} hidden layer, S_i is the input data, and b_j & b_k denotes the bias values of the first and second hidden layer. Instead of choosing the weight and bias values of the network randomly, here wavelet kernel is applied to get the most fit weight and bias values of the network that will enhances the performance of the network. Given a mother wavelet function, $\psi(W)$ whose scale factor and translation factor are p and q respectively, the wavelet basis function can be expressed as:

$$\psi_{p,q}(W) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{|p|}} \psi\left(\frac{W-q}{p}\right) \quad (21)$$

Tensor products of numerous one-dimensional wavelet functions (1DWF) can be used to express a multidimensional wavelet function, according to tensor product theory:

$$\psi(W) = \prod_{i=1}^n \psi(W_i) \quad (22)$$

Where n denotes the number 1DWF, when the multidimensional wavelet function is written in tensor product form; and W_i is the independent variable of the i^{th} one-dimensional wavelet function. In accordance with Equation (31), a translation-invariant kernel function can be constructed:

$$K(W, W') = \prod_{i=1}^n \psi\left(\frac{W_i - W'_i}{p}\right) \quad (23)$$

The Morlet wavelet (MV) is used to construct the WK function in this paper. The MV function is denoted as

$$\psi(W) = \cos(1.75W) \exp\left(-\frac{W^2}{2}\right) \quad (24)$$

The WK function constructed from the MV function is

$$K(W, W') = \prod_{i=1}^n \left[\cos\left(1.75 \times \frac{W_i - W'_i}{p}\right) \exp\left(-\frac{(W_i - W'_i)^2}{2p^2}\right) \right] \quad (25)$$

Where W_i are the i^{th} components of W .

Because the WK function is built using the wavelet function's translation-invariant kernel, it inherits the wavelet function's multi-scale approximation properties. As a result, using a WK function as the kernel function in MLPNN will improve classification. The above kernel computations are performed on the weight values ranging from the input layer to the first hidden layer. Similarly, computations are performed for the weight values from the first hidden layer to the second hidden layer, the weight values from the second hidden layer to the output layer, and the bias values of all layers. After obtaining the weight and bias values for all layers, the final output layer computation for the ID framework is expressed as

$$O_m = \sum_{k,m=1}^n A_f(W_{km}H_k + b_m) \quad (26)$$

Where W_{km} denotes the weight value of the k^{th} hidden layer to the m^{th} output layer, b_m denotes the bias value of the output layer and A_f denotes the sigmoid activation function. After classification, the total error is estimated as follows

$$E = \frac{1}{T} \sum_{o=1}^T \sum_{m=1}^n [D_m - O_m]^2 \quad (27)$$

Where D_m denotes the desired output, O_m denotes the predicted output, and T denotes number of training instances. The results of proposed WKMLPNN consist of two types of output such as data with intrusion, and data without intrusion. The data containing intrusion is avoided and non-intruded data is safely stored in cloud with the help of IECC.

3.4 IECC based Data Encryption

Elliptic Curve Cryptography (ECC) is commonly known as a kind of public-key cryptography (PKC) that uses a pair of keys: a private key along with a public key, as well as a set of actions associated with the keys to perform cryptographic functions. Using elliptic curve mathematics, ECC produces security betwixt key pairs for public-key encryption. Unlike RSA, ECC bases its approach to public-key cryptographic systems on how elliptic curves are algebraically structured over finite fields. As a result, ECC generates keys that are mathematically more difficult to crack. As a result, ECC is regarded as the next-generation

implementation of PKC, as well as being more secure than RSA. ECC, on the other hand, generates a random number for the generation of the private key. This will increase the chances of intruders predicting the private key easily by applying all possible values within the range of generated private key, and if they predicted the value of the private key they will easily get the access to the someone's or DO's data which is stored on a cloud. Weak random number generation for private key generation processes generally requires less processing power and does not use the system's precious, finite entropy sources. While such generation may have very useful features, they may also be used to break cryptography. As a result, the data may be vulnerable to certain types of attacks. So to overcome such drawbacks, here private key of the ECC algorithm is generated by combining two different models such as the chaotic scaled Zhongtang system (CSZS) and SHA-256. Firstly using the CSZS, fast and highly random data is generated. Then the generated random sequence using CSZS is hashed using the SHA-256 algorithm. The resultant data of this hashing value is considered a private key in the ECC algorithm. Thus, the use of random numbers with CSZS and generation of the private key by combining SHA-256 and ZSCS avoids predictable keys of the unauthorized user and denies access to the DO's data in the cloud. This novel key generation process-based encryption in ECC increases the data information entropy while requiring less processing time, resulting in a fast and secure encryption system. This CSZS and SHA-512 hashing based key generation model for ECC is named (CSZSHECC). The mathematical representation of the CSZSHECC is shown here.

$$z^2 = x^3 + px + q \quad (28)$$

Where p and q are the integers. The encryption technique's strength is solely determined by the mechanism used to generate the key during the encryption process. Two types of keys are generated in the proposed system. They are the public key used to encrypt data and the private key used to decrypt data. Consider a base point B_p on the curve. The private key of the algorithm is generated by combining CSZS and SHA 256 which is expressed as follows

$$P_{rk} = CSZS * SHA256 \quad (29)$$

Where $CSZS = \bar{x} + \bar{y} + \bar{z}$ and $SHA256$ indicates the SHA 256 hash function. The CSZS includes three phases such as \bar{x} , \bar{y} , and \bar{z} . The three phases of CZSZ are produced from the initial conditions $(x, y, \text{and } z)$ and system parameters $k_1, k_2, k_3, k_4, k_5, k_6, \text{and } k_7$ as follows

$$\begin{aligned} \bar{x} &= k_1 y - k_2 x \\ \bar{y} &= k_3 x + k_4 y - k_5 x z^2 \\ \bar{z} &= -k_6 x - k_7 z + z x^2 \end{aligned} \quad (30)$$

These scaling operations were carried out in order to give the random number generator a more appropriate structure. With the initial values and system parameters in equation, the phase portraits of the scaled system are obtained (31)

$$k_1 = 80, k_2 = 40, k_3 = 5, k_4 = 10, k_5 = 2, k_6 = 10, k_7 = 15$$

$$\&(x, y, z) \in (-5, 5) \quad (31)$$

Then generate a public key Pu_k by performing the following operation.

$$Pu_k = Pr_k * B_p \quad (32)$$

The values obtained from the user are encrypted after the key is generated. The encrypted data contains two cipher texts, which are mathematically represented as follows.

$$C_1 = (R_d * B_p) \quad (33)$$

$$C_2 = (O_d + (R_d * Pu_k)) \quad (34)$$

Where O_d denotes the original sensitive data after the classification process and R_d denotes the random number, which is in the range of 1 to $n-1$. The encrypted data is stored in cloud. After the DO is authenticated at the cloud end for data access, the encrypted data is given to the user and the decryption of the encryption data is performed with the private key. The decryption process performed at the user end is expressed by the following operation

$$O_d = ((C_2 - P_{rk}) * C_1) \quad (35)$$

3.5 Access Permission for Data Download

The user authentication is also performed for the user to retrieve the data from the cloud storage. The user provides his user ID and password to CSP, who verifies the information. The CSP prompts the user to enter a hash code after verifying the user credentials and password. If the hash code entered by the user matches the hash code stored in the CSP database, an OTP is sent to the user's registered mobile number provided during the enrollment process. The user is required to enter the sent OTP to the CSP in order to complete the certification process; the CSP compares it to the OTP generated and thus verifies the mobile number if it matches; otherwise, the data recovery requests are denied.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Here the outcomes of the proposed ID and data security model are discussed. The performance efficiency of the proposed models is evaluated by comparing them to state-of-the-art techniques in terms of some performance metrics. The proposed model's experimentation is carried out in Python using the Cloudsim tool, and on a PC installed with Windows 10 operating system, Intel i7 processor, and 8 GB RAM. The dataset used to train the proposed WKMLPNN is the publicly available NSL-KDD dataset. The dataset contains five million records, with each record containing 41 features. The attack classes in the NSL-KDD dataset are classified as Probe attacks, Remote to Local (R2L) attacks, User to Root (U2R) attacks, and Denial of Service attacks. A binary class attribute is present in this dataset (normal and attacked data). It also has a sufficient number of training and test instances,

making it feasible for running the experiments. First, the performance of the DL-based ID models is evaluated in terms of f-measure, accuracy, false alarm rate, and training time. The existing models taken for comparison are T2FNN [19], ensemble model [20], BP-NN [21], SVNN [22], and HLDNS [23]. Each existing model uses different datasets for ID and different working platforms with unique configurations for performance analysis. Here the results showed are the results attained for each model when applied in proposed design configurations and the NSL-KDD dataset. Table 1 demonstrates the results of the models for four different attacks in the dataset in terms of f-measure and accuracy.

Table 1: F-measure and Accuracy of the models

(a)

Models/Attacks	DoS	Probe	R2L	U2R
T2FNN	88.76	72.34	89.65	87.67
Ensemble model	90.88	80.97	91.65	89.54
BP-NN	92.12	85.76	92.23	91.23
SVNN	92.34	88.76	90.45	93.45
HLDNS	94.23	90.32	95.98	92.34
Proposed WKMLPNN with TGSA	98.99	96.67	98.34	97.99

(b)

Models/Attacks	DoS	Probe	R2L	U2R
T2FNN	87.23	70.21	89.88	87.56
Ensemble model	90.23	80.12	92.23	89.45
BP-NN	92.12	84.98	92.99	91.12
SVNN	92.45	88.89	90.21	93.65
HLDNS	94.02	89.65	95.43	92.67
Proposed WKMLPNN with TGSA	98.78	96.53	98.56	98.65

Table 1 confirms the superior performance of the proposed WKMLPNN with the TGSA model for intrusions detection in the cloud over existing algorithms. The proposed model attains a higher level of f-measure and accuracy for all four types of attacks when compared to existing models. For detecting DoS attacks, the proposed model achieves the f-measure of 98.99, whereas the existing techniques such as T2FNN, ensemble model, BP-NN, SVNN, and HLDNS give the f-measure of 88.76, 90.88, 92.12, 92.34, and 94.23 which are lower than the WKMLPNN with TGSA model. Similarly, WKMLPNN with TGSA gives the highest accuracy of 98.78 for DoS attack detection, whereas the existing models give a lower accuracy (T2FNN-87.23, ensemble model-90.23, BP-NN-92.12, SVNN-92.45, and HLDNS-

94.02) when compared with the proposed model. The results of models show that the WKMLPNN with optimal feature selection not only obtains the best performance for DoS attack detection. It shows a remarkable performance for the other three types of attacks too. The comparison of detection models regarding false alarm rate and training/processing time is given in figure 3.

Figure 3: False alarm rate and training time of the models

The false alarm rate shows the value of data which is falsely reported as an intrusion from the overall data sample. From figure 3 (a), it is confirmed that the proposed WKMLPNN with TGSA gives a lesser false alarm rate when compared to existing models for all four attacks. The WKMLPNN with TGSA gives the false alarm rate of 2.12 for DoS attacks, whereas the existing T2FNN, ensemble model, BP-NN, SVNN, and HLDNS give the false alarm rate of 6.43, 5.43, 4.99, 4.21, and 3.56, which are higher than the proposed model. Likewise, when comparing the false alarm rate of models for the other three attacks such as Probe, R2L, and U2R, the proposed model gives the lowest false alarm rate than others. Figure 3 (b) shows the training time of the models for attack detection. The WKMLPNN with TGSA takes very less

time to train the data when compared to the existing T2FNN (8.543), ensemble model (6.543), BP-NN (5.897), SVNN (5.234), and HLDNS (4.124). So from the outcomes of classifiers for ID, it was concluded that the WKMLPNN with TGSA attains the best performance over exiting techniques in terms of all compared performance metrics for all types of attacks in the dataset. This is because of the optimal feature selection model and wavelet kernel-based weight and bias selection. Both optimal feature selection and wavelet kernel helps the classifier to achieve accurate detection, lesser errors in classification and minimized training time. Next, the performance analysis is done for the proposed and existing encryption models for cloud data storage. The existing frameworks taken for encryption comparison are CryptoGA [24], Enhanced Blowfish Algorithm (EBFA) [25], ECC-Blowfish [26], Lightweight cryptography (LWC) [27] and CRT-RSA [28]. The metrics taken for comparison are encryption time (ET), decryption time (DT) and data integrity rate.

(a)

(b)

Figure 4: ET and DT of the models

Fig. 4 demonstrates the ET and DT results of the models. The comparison is based on the number of normal data after ID. In figure 5 (a), when the number of data is 100, the ET of the

proposed IECC is 4092, whereas the existent techniques such as CryptoGA, EBFA, ECC-Blowfish, LWC and CRT-RSA obtain the ETs of 6543, 8654, 9032, 9801, and 10001. When the number of data increases, the ET of the models also increases but the IECC takes minimal time for performing encryption on the data when compared to the previous state of art techniques. The DT analysis of the proposed, as well as prior models, is cited in fig 5 (b). The time taken by the proposed IECC to decrypt the 100 number of encrypted data is 4088ms which is very lower when contrasted to the existing approaches. Because for the same 100 data, the existing CryptoGA, EBFA, ECC-Blowfish, LWC and CRT-RSA take the DTs of 6545, 8655, 9031, 9801, and 10003. So when comparing the results, it was stated that the proposed encryption model achieves better results over existing models for performing both encryption and decryption of data with lesser time. This is because of the efficient key generation using hashing technique and CSZS. Next, the integrity level of data (ILD) when using the proposed encryption model is checked, the results are shown in figure 5.

Figure 5: Integrity level of the models

ILD is a security parameter that referred to the number of data that are not altered to the number of data transmitted. The proposed IECC based cloud data storage system achieves a higher amount of ILD for all counts of data. It achieves the ILD in the ranges of 94.5% to 96.43% for all numbers of data. But the existing models attain the lowest ILD when compared with the proposed model. These performance results depict that the proposed IECC method outperforms others by achieving a higher ILD. Here the higher level of ILD is attained for the proposed IECC model because of the complex key generation process using hashing technique and ZSCS function. So the possibility of getting decrypted data from cloud storage is very low in the proposed system. So from the detection and encryption outcomes, it is confirmed that the proposed approach achieves superior performance for both malware detection and secure cloud storage over existing approaches.

5. CONCLUSION

This paper proposes a WKMLPNN based IDS and IECC based cloud storage system with SHA-256 hashing based user authentication. For analyzing the effectiveness of the proposed models, the results of the proposed models are compared with the existing models regarding some performance metrics. From the results of classification models it was observed that the proposed WKMLPNN achieves better results for f-measure accuracy, and false alarm rate for all four types of attacks in the dataset when compared with the existing mechanisms. In addition, the proposed model attains the lowest training time for training the system to identify the intrusions. The inclusion of novel optimal feature selection and WK helps the MLPNN for getting higher accuracy, lower errors, and lower training time in ID. Likewise, the IECC algorithm shows its best performance in secure cloud storage over other encryption models concerning the metrics of encryption time, decryption time, and ILD for all numbers of data. With these mechanisms, the SHA-256 hashing based technique offers an efficient authentication system for cloud storage and this mechanism avoids the data to be retrieved from unauthorized users. So from the results, the paper concludes that a WKMLPNN with optimal feature selection and IECC based encryption mechanisms are very useful for performing ID more accurately and for offering the very secure cloud storage for DO's data without the possibility of an attack on their data on cloud platform. In future, the work will be extended to identify the more kinds of attacks which are performed over a cloud network and the encryption models will be introduced with efficient data duplication mechanisms for eliminating excessive copies of data and decreasing storage capacity requirements.

Statements and Declarations

Ethics approval and consent to participate

Not applicable

Consent for publication

Not applicable

Availability of data and materials

The dataset used for the present work is the publicly available NSL-KDD dataset, which is available in <https://www.kaggle.com/datasets/hassan06/nslkdd>.

Funding

Not applicable

Authors' contributions

The authors confirm contribution to the paper as follows: study conception and design: 1st Author, 2nd Author; data collection: 2nd Author; analysis and interpretation of results: 1st Author; Manuscript Written: 1st Author; Supervision: 2nd Author.

Acknowledgements

I would like to express my special thanks of gratitude to my guide (Dr. M. Safish Mary) who gave me the golden opportunity to do this wonderful paper on the topic (Cloud Security), which also helped me in doing a lot of Research and i came to know about so many new things. I am really thankful to her.

Competing interest

The authors declare that there are no conflicts of interest regarding the publication of this paper.

REFERENCES

- [1] Varun Prabhakaran, and Ashokkumar Kulandasamy, “Hybrid semantic deep learning architecture and optimal advanced encryption standard key management scheme for secure cloud storage and intrusion detection”, *Neural Computing and Applications*, vol. 33, no. 21, pp. 14459-14479, 2021.
- [2] Chirag Modi, and Dhiren Patel, “A feasible approach to intrusion detection in virtual network layer of Cloud computing”, *Sādhanā*, vol. 43, no. 7, pp. 1-16, 2018.
- [3] Chinnasamy P, and Deepalakshmi P, “HCAC-EHR: hybrid cryptographic access control for secure EHR retrieval in healthcare cloud”, *Journal of Ambient Intelligence and Humanized Computing*, vol. 13, no. 2, pp. 1001-1019, 2022.
- [4] Mayuranathan M, Murugan M, and Dhanakoti V, “Best features based intrusion detection system by RBM model for detecting DDoS in cloud environment”, *Journal of Ambient Intelligence and Humanized Computing*, vol. 12, no. 3, pp. 3609-3619, 2021.
- [5] Janusz Kacprzyk, “Lecture notes in networks and systems”, 2019.
- [6] Vikas Goyal, and Chander Kant, “An effective hybrid encryption algorithm for ensuring cloud data security”, *Big data analytics*, pp. 195-210, 2018.
- [7] Ünal Çavuşoğlu, “A new hybrid approach for intrusion detection using machine learning methods”, *Applied Intelligence*, vol. 49, no. 7, pp. 2735-2761, 2019.
- [8] Nilesh Kunhare, Ritu Tiwari, and Joydip Dhar, “Particle swarm optimization and feature selection for intrusion detection system”, *Sādhanā*, vol. 45, no. 1, pp. 1-14, 2020.
- [9] Dželila Mehanović, Dino Kečo, Jasmin Kevrić, Samed Jukić, Adnan Miljković, and Zerina Mašetić, “Feature selection using cloud-based parallel genetic algorithm for intrusion detection data classification”, *Neural Computing and Applications*, vol. 33, no. 18, pp. 11861-11873, 2021.
- [10] Kamalakanta Sethi, Sai Rupesh E, Rahul Kumar, Padmalochan Bera, and Venu Madhav Y, “A context-aware robust intrusion detection system: a reinforcement learning-based approach”, *International Journal of Information Security*, vol. 19, no. 6, pp. 657-678, 2020.
- [11] Amirah Alshammari and Abdulaziz Aldribi, “Apply machine learning techniques to detect malicious network traffic in cloud computing”, *Journal of Big Data*, 2021, <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40537-021-00475-1>.
- [12] Aws Naser Jaber, and Shafiq Ul Rehman, “FCM–SVM based intrusion detection system for cloud computing environment”, *Cluster Computing*, vol. 23, no. 4, pp. 3221-3231, 2020.
- [13] Elham Besharati, Marjan Naderan, and Ehsan Namjoo, “LR-HIDS: logistic regression host-based intrusion detection system for cloud environments”, *Journal of Ambient Intelligence and Humanized Computing*, vol. 10, no. 9, pp. 3669-3692, 2019.
- [14] Jitendra Kumar Seth, and Satish Chandra, “MIDS: Metaheuristic based intrusion detection system for cloud using k-NN and MGWO”, in *International Conference on Advances in Computing and Data Sciences*, Singapore, pp. 411-420, 2018.
- [15] Geeta Kocher, and Gulshan Kumar, “Machine learning and deep learning methods for intrusion detection systems: recent developments and challenges”, *Soft Computing*, vol. 25, no. 15, pp. 9731-9763, 2021.

- [16] Weiru Wang, Yanfen Gan, Chi-Man Vong, and Chuanguan Chen, "Homo-ELM: Fully homomorphic extreme learning machine", *International Journal of Machine Learning and Cybernetics* 11, no. 7, pp. 1531-1540, 2020.
- [17] Balasubramanian Prabhu Kavin, Sannasi Ganapathy, U. Kanimozhi, and Arputharaj Kannan, "An enhanced security framework for secured data storage and communications in cloud using ECC, access control and LDSA", *Wireless Personal Communications*, vol. 115, no. 2, pp. 1107-1135, 2020.
- [18] Dilip Venkata Kumar Vengala, D. Kavitha, and A. P. Kumar, "Three factor authentication system with modified ECC based secured data transfer: untrusted cloud environment", *Complex & Intelligent Systems*, pp. 1-14, 2021.
- [19] Doddi Srilatha, and Gopal K. Shyam, "Cloud-based intrusion detection using kernel fuzzy clustering and optimal type-2 fuzzy neural network", *Cluster Computing*, vol. 24, no. 3, pp. 2657-2672, 2021.
- [20] Parul Singh, and Virender Ranga, "Attack and intrusion detection in cloud computing using an ensemble learning approach", *International Journal of Information Technology*, vol. 13, no. 2, pp. 565-571, 2021.
- [21] Linbin Wen, "Cloud Computing Intrusion Detection Technology Based on BP-NN", *Wireless Personal Communications*, pp. 1-18, 2021.
- [22] Siva Rama Krishna Tummalapalli, and A. S. N. Chakravarthy, "Intrusion detection system for cloud forensics using bayesian fuzzy clustering and optimization based SVNN", *Evolutionary Intelligence*, vol. 14, no. 2, pp. 699-709, 2021.
- [23] Rajendra Patil, Harsha Dudeja, and Chirag Modi, "Designing an efficient security framework for detecting intrusions in virtual network of cloud computing", *Computers & Security*, vol. 85, pp. 402-422, 2019.
- [24] Muhammad Tahir, Muhammad Sardaraz, Zahid Mehmood, and Shakoor Muhammad, "CryptoGA: a cryptosystem based on genetic algorithm for cloud data security", *Cluster Computing*, vol. 24, no. 2, pp. 739-752, 2021.
- [25] Balamurugan, K., Kuppusamy, A., Latchoumi, T. P., Banerjee, A., Sinha, A., Biswas, A., & Subramanian, A. K. (2022). Multi-response Optimization of Turning Parameters for Cryogenically Treated and Tempered WC-Co Inserts. *Journal of The Institution of Engineers (India): Series D*, 1-12. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40033-021-00321-x>
- [26] Latchoumi, T. P., Kalusuraman, G., Banu, J. F., Yookesh, T. L., Ezhilarasi, T. P., & Balamurugan, K. (2021, November). Enhancement in manufacturing systems using Grey-Fuzzy and LK-SVM approach. In *2021 IEEE International Conference on Intelligent Systems, Smart and Green Technologies (ICISSGT)* (pp. 72-78). IEEE. doi: 10.1109/ICISSGT52025.2021.00026.
- [27] Banu, J. F., Muneeshwari, P., Raja, K., Suresh, S., Latchoumi, T. P., & Deepan, S. (2022, January). Ontology Based Image Retrieval by Utilizing Model Annotations and Content. In *2022 12th International Conference on Cloud Computing, Data Science & Engineering (Confluence)* (pp. 300-305). IEEE. doi: 10.1109/Confluence52989.2022.9734194.
- [28] Vanga, M. S. R., Vijayaraj, J., Kolluru, P., & Latchoumi, T. P. (2022). Semantics-Driven Safety Measures in Distributed Big Data Systems on IoT. In *Advanced Computational Paradigms and Hybrid Intelligent Computing* (pp. 251-259). Springer, Singapore. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-981-16-4369-9_26
- [29] Venkata Koti Reddy Gangireddy, Srihari Kannan, and Karthik Subburathinam, "Implementation of enhanced blowfish algorithm in cloud environment", *Journal of Ambient Intelligence and Humanized Computing*, vol. 12, no. 3, pp. 3999-4005, 2021.
- [30] Chinnasamy P, Padmavathi S, Swathy R, and Rakesh S, "Efficient data security using hybrid cryptography on cloud computing", In *Inventive Communication and Computational Technologies*, pp. 537-547. Springer, Singapore, 2021.

- [31] Fursan Thabit, Sharaf Alhomdy, Abdulrazzaq HA Al-Ahdal, and Sudhir Jagtap, "A new lightweight cryptographic algorithm for enhancing data security in cloud computing", *Global Transitions Proceedings*, vol. 2, no. 1, pp. 91-99.
- [32] Rabia Abid, Celestine Iwendi, Abdul Rehman Javed, Muhammad Rizwan, Zunera Jalil, Joseph Henry Anajemba, and Cresantus Biamba, "An optimised homomorphic CRT-RSA algorithm for secure and efficient communication", *Personal and Ubiquitous Computing*, pp. 1-14, 2021.
- [33] Latchoumi, T. P., Swathi, R., Vidyasri, P., & Balamurugan, K. (2022, March). Develop New Algorithm To Improve Safety On WMSN In Health Disease Monitoring. In *2022 International Mobile and Embedded Technology Conference (MECON)* (pp. 357-362). IEEE. doi: 10.1109/MECON53876.2022.9752178.
- [34] Latchoumi, T. P., Kothandaraman, R., & Balamurugan, K.. (2022). Implementation of Visual Clustering Strategy in Self-Organizing Map for Wear Studies Samples Printed Using FDM. *Traitement du Signal*, 39(2). DOI: 10.18280/ts.390215
- [35] Venkatesh, A. P., Latchoumi, T. P., Chezhian Babu, S., Balamurugan, K., Ganesan, S., Ruban, M., & Mulugeta, L. (2022). Multiparametric Optimization on Influence of Ethanol and Biodiesel Blends on Nanocoated Engine by Full Factorial Design. *Journal of Nanomaterials*, 2022. <https://doi.org/10.1155/2022/5350122>
- [36] Garikapati, P. R., Balamurugan, K., Latchoumi, T. P., & Shankar, G. (2022). A Quantitative Study of Small Dataset Machining by Agglomerative Hierarchical Cluster and K-Medoid. In *Emergent Converging Technologies and Biomedical Systems* (pp. 717-727). Springer, Singapore. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-981-16-8774-7_59.